

Cueing-assisted gamified augmented-reality gait-and-balance rehabilitation at home for people with Parkinson's disease: protocol of a pragmatic randomized controlled trial implemented in the clinical pathway

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8 **Keywords:** augmented reality, gamified exercise, cueing, Parkinson's disease, clinical
9 feasibility, effectiveness.

10

11 **Abstract**

12 **Background** Physiotherapy in the clinic is highly recommended for improving gait, balance and falls
13 risk in people with Parkinson's disease. In addition, technology may help boost unsupervised
14 exercise hours at home. Stroll is an augmented-reality (AR) neurorehabilitation platform for
15 delivering gait-and-balance exercises onto AR glasses that can be performed under direct supervision
16 of the therapist in the clinic, but also independently at home. Stroll AR also has the option to
17 integrate AR cueing in gait-and-balance exercises to assist people with more severe mobility
18 impairments in performing the exercises. The objective of this pragmatic randomized controlled trial
19 (RCT) on Stroll AR is to examine its clinical feasibility and effectiveness for improving indicators
20 of gait, balance and falls risk. A secondary objective is to evaluate procedures for tailoring assistive
21 AR cues.

22 **Methods** 80-100 people with Parkinson's disease (Hoehn and Yahr stages 1-3) with gait and/or
23 balance impairments will participate in this study. This study is a pragmatic RCT in which all
24 participants follow the same procedure. After a baseline assessment (T0), participants will start with
25 a 6-week usual care control period, followed by a midterm assessment (T1). Subsequently,
26 participants will undergo two weeks of in-clinic familiarization with Stroll AR. Then, participants
27 will start with the 6-week Stroll AR intervention at home, followed by a final in-clinic assessment
28 (T2). The primary study parameters are feasibility (i.e., safety, adherence, performance and user
29 experience) and effectiveness for improving indicators of gait, balance and falls risk. For the
30 statistical analyses on effectiveness, participants will be allocated to control (using T0-T1 change
31 data) or intervention (using T1-T2 change data) groups using multiple (n=20) randomizations.
32 Recruitment started in May 2024 and the last T2 assessment is expected in January 2025.

33 **Discussion** The design of this particular pragmatic RCT will demonstrate feasibility and
34 effectiveness in a real-world setting and in a representative population. Stroll AR may facilitate the
35 transition from supervised care in the clinic to independent care at home, providing a platform for
36 delivering individualized treatment, assisted with AR cues when deemed beneficial, for improving
37 gait, balance and falls risk in people with Parkinson's disease.

40 **1. Introduction**

41 People with Parkinson's disease face motor symptoms that limit activities of daily life (1-3), restrict
42 participation (1, 2), and elevate falls risk (4). Physiotherapy for people with Parkinson's disease aims
43 to 'maximize quality of movement, functional independence and general fitness, and to minimize
44 secondary complications while supporting self-management and participation, and optimizing safety'
45 (5). It addresses five core aspects: physical capacity, transfers, manual activities, balance and gait (2),
46 with balance and gait impairments often being indicators for an elevated falls risk (4). People with
47 Parkinson's disease often have a sedentary lifestyle (6), which may further worsen motor symptoms
48 and associated falls risk. Physiotherapy, including prescribed unsupervised exercises at home, is
49 highly recommended for improving gait, balance and falls risk (1, 2, 7). That is, guidelines specific
50 for people with Parkinson's disease recommend to exercise for at least 150 minutes per week at a
51 moderate to vigorous intensity, which can include (brisk) walking, balance training and strength
52 exercises (1, 7, 8), tailored to the specific needs of the person with Parkinson's disease for the best
53 outcome (9). However, this is often a difficult exercise target to reach and monitoring of the
54 adherence often relies on self-reporting (10).

55 Emerging technology may help boost unsupervised exercise adherence at home (11). A
56 promising technology in that regard is Strolll, an augmented-reality (AR) neurorehabilitation
57 platform for delivering gait and balance exercises for Parkinson's disease onto state-of-the-art AR
58 glasses (www.strolll.co) like Magic Leap 2 and Microsoft HoloLens 2. Various gamified and
59 structured therapeutic exercises have been co-designed with people with Parkinson's disease,
60 therapists and other stakeholders for gait and balance practice, aimed at obtaining engaging, effective
61 therapy at high adherence (12). The Strolll AR platform comprises seven AR exercises that can be
62 performed under direct supervision of the therapist in the clinic (Figure 1A), but also independently
63 by people with Parkinson's disease at home (Figure 1B), remotely prescribed and tailored by their
64 therapists. Recently, Hardeman et al. (12) examined in a waitlist-controlled trial the feasibility and
65 potential efficacy of Reality DTx[®], the precursor of Strolll AR, for improving gait, balance and falls
66 risk in people with Parkinson's disease in a research setting. This 6-week remotely prescribed home-
67 based AR program was safe, adherable, usable and well-accepted, with targeted intervention effects
68 for improving indicators of gait, balance and falls risk (12). Building on these promising results,
69 obtained in a research setting, the current study aims to evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of
70 Strolll AR implemented in the clinical pathway, where therapists from more than ten physical or
71 exercise therapy clinics will integrate the Strolll AR platform with usual care, starting supervised in
72 the clinic and then performed independently at home by people with Parkinson's disease.

73 New to the Strolll AR platform is the option to integrate AR cueing in gait-and-balance
74 exercises, which will assist people with more severe mobility impairments, like freezing of gait and
75 festination, in performing the exercises. Cueing in the form of spatial (like visual lines or stepping
76 targets) or temporal (like an acoustic rhythm) external stimuli aids the initiation, facilitation or
77 modification of gait, generally with immediate effect (13-15). The effects of AR cueing delivered on
78 state-of-the-art AR glasses with large vertical AR fields of views like Microsoft HoloLens 2 and
79 Magic Leap 2 is not too dissimilar anymore from traditional cueing options. For example, our
80 previous work showed that AR cueing alleviated freezing of gait in people with long and/or many
81 freezing episodes (16) and that the gait-modifying effects of AR cueing were similar to those of real-
82 world cueing (e.g., in terms of step-length and walking-speed modulation; (17)). As cueing is not a
83 one-size-fits-all solution (18, 19), the AR cues in the current study will be tailored to the individual's
84 preferences (e.g., some people benefit from 3D cues to step over, others from 2D cues to step onto

85 (19, 20)) and gait characteristics (e.g., intercue distances fitting a person's step length and width) in
86 an attempt to yield optimal cueing effects during Strolll's AR gait-and-balance exercises.

87 The objective of this pragmatic randomized controlled trial (RCT) on Strolll AR, an
88 individualized AR gait-and-balance exercise platform complemented with tailored AR cues when
89 deemed beneficial, is to examine its clinical feasibility and effectiveness. We expect that Strolll AR is
90 i) clinically feasible in terms of safety, adherence, performance and user experience (i.e., for both
91 people with Parkinson's disease and their therapists) and ii) effective for improving indicators of gait,
92 balance and falls risk in people with Parkinson's disease. The secondary objective of this study is to
93 evaluate procedures for tailoring assistive AR cues to individuals when deemed beneficial in
94 performing the AR gait-and-balance exercises. We expect that many of the participants, particularly
95 those with more severe mobility impairments like freezing of gait and festination, could benefit from
96 assistive AR cues integrated in the AR exercises and that they use a variety of cue settings, thereby
97 substantiating the necessity to personalize AR cues.

98 **2. Methods and Analysis**

99 **2.1. Study design**

100 This study is a fully blinded two-armed pragmatic RCT, which will be executed in the Netherlands
101 implemented at multiple physical or exercise therapy clinics. The study consists of three in-clinic
102 assessments performed by the participant's own therapist (Figure 2). After a baseline assessment
103 (T0), participants will start with a 6-week usual care control period, followed by a midterm
104 assessment (T1). Subsequently, participants will undergo two weeks of in-clinic familiarization with
105 Strolll AR supervised by their therapist. Then, participants will start with the 6-week Strolll AR
106 intervention at home integrated with usual care, followed by the final in-clinic assessment (T2).

107 The definition of a pragmatic RCT is that the intervention is tested in a real-world population in
108 a real-world setting (i.e., the clinic), with an appropriate comparison arm (i.e., usual care alone in the
109 current study) and relevant outcomes to determine its effectiveness (21, 22). Special trial designs can
110 be considered. In this particular pragmatic RCT all participants follow the same T0-control-T1-
111 intervention-T2 procedure, suitable for both between-groups and within-subjects comparisons of the
112 Strolll AR intervention effects as well as for evaluating its clinical feasibility. With regard to the
113 between-groups comparison, participants will be allocated to control (using T0-T1 change data) or
114 intervention (using T1-T2 change data) groups using multiple (n=20) two-armed randomizations
115 (Figure 3). The randomization will be predefined by an independent person using a Matlab (23)
116 script, locked with a date and timestamp, and kept concealed from participants, therapists and
117 researchers. After the final T2 assessment of the last participant, the 20 randomizations of
118 participants over control and intervention groups will be revealed to the researchers and applied in
119 the data analysis (as detailed in section 2.7.3). Participants, therapists, and researchers will therefore
120 all be blind to group allocation during the study. This design, in which all participants receive the
121 Strolll AR intervention, also allows for a complementary within-subjects evaluation of the
122 intervention effect (i.e., being less susceptible to between-subjects variation than aforementioned
123 between-groups evaluation), whilst at the same time providing ample information on the clinical
124 feasibility of the Strolll AR platform implemented in the clinical pathway in terms of its safety,
125 adherence, performance and user experience (i.e., from both participants' and therapists'
126 perspectives). Moreover, a design with the same procedure for all participants makes implementation
127 of this study in the clinical pathway easier (hence the term pragmatic RCT) and potentially reduces
128 drop-out rate because no participants are withheld from receiving the intervention due to the
129 randomization.

130 **2.2.Procedure and outcomes**

131 After enrollment, the study consists of three in-clinic assessments spread out over 14 weeks,
132 demarcating a usual-care control period and a Stroll AR intervention period (Figure 2). Below we
133 describe the procedure for each of these parts of the design.

134 **2.2.1. Participant enrollment (C1, C2): enrollment and informed consent**

135 The therapist will inform eligible participants about the study. If people are interested, they will
136 receive a flyer with instructions on how to send their contact details to the researchers. Upon receipt
137 of contact details of a potential participant, the researcher will call this person to provide more
138 information about the study (C1, Figure 3). Hereafter, potential participants will receive the
139 participant information letter by mail or email. A week after receiving the participant information
140 letter, the researcher will again call the potential participant (C2, Figure 3) to answer any questions
141 and to ask if he or she wants to participate. If so, in- and exclusion criteria will be checked by the
142 researcher (to the extent possible, otherwise criteria will be evaluated during the baseline assessment
143 session T0). Furthermore, the potential participant will be informed that the medication should
144 remain stable during the study. If the potential participant is eligible, he or she will be asked to sign
145 the informed consent form, after which the researcher also signs the informed consent form and
146 notifies the therapist that the person can start with the pragmatic RCT. Written informed consent
147 must be given before commencing with the baseline assessment (T0).

148 **2.2.2. Baseline assessment (T0): characterization and effectiveness**

149 The baseline assessment serves to characterize the study sample and to provide baseline values for
150 evaluating the effectiveness of Stroll AR (see also Table 1). Study parameters used to characterize
151 the participants are demographics (i.e., age, gender, disease duration) and current medication use
152 (i.e., the Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose [LEDD]). Questionnaires to describe the participant
153 population are the Montreal Cognitive Assessment [MoCA; (24)], Movement Disorders Society
154 Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale [MDS-UPDRS; (25)], New Freezing of Gait Questionnaire
155 [NFOGQ; (26)], Physical Activity Scale for the Elderly [PASE; (27)], Cumulative Illness Rating
156 Scale [CIRS; (28)], and 12-month falls history. All these outcomes will be collected using online
157 questionnaires, except for the MoCA and MDS-UPDRS part Ia, III and IV, which will be
158 administered in the clinic by the therapist. To be able to evaluate the potential effects of Stroll AR
159 for improving indicators of gait, balance and falls risk, the following standard clinical tests will be
160 administered by the therapists: Timed Up-and-Go test (TUG; (29)), Five Times Sit-to-Stand test
161 (FTSTS; (30)), 10-meter walk test (10MWT; (31)) and Mini Balance Evaluation Scale Test (Mini-
162 BESTest; (32)). In addition, participants will fill out the Falls Efficacy Scale International (FES-I;
163 (33)).

164 **2.2.3. Usual care (6-weeks)**

165 During the usual-care control period, participants will not receive any additional training or
166 instructions related to the Stroll AR intervention.

167 **2.2.4. Midterm assessment (T1): effectiveness**

168 For the midterm assessment, the standard clinical tests of gait, balance and falls-risk indicators
169 (TUG, FTSTS, 10MWT, Mini-BESTest; Table 1) will again be administered by the therapist. In
170 addition, the participants are asked to fill out the FES-I and 6-week falls history (to assess falls
171 during the usual-care period) questionnaires at home (Table 1).

172 **2.2.5. Practice with Strolll AR intervention supervised in clinic (2 weeks)**

173 To make the participant familiar with the Strolll AR platform technology and procedures and to
174 allow the therapist to evaluate safety aspects, the Strolll AR intervention starts with 1 to 3 supervised
175 in-clinic sessions of (cueing-assisted) personalized AR exercises.

176 In these supervised sessions in the clinic, the therapist will also test and validate procedures to
177 select and tailor effective assistive AR cues from a library of different AR cues (see Supplementary
178 Material for the types of cues used in this study). This is needed for two reasons: 1) to test the
179 premise that a one-size-fits-all cue does not exist as there is heterogeneity in effect of cues among
180 participants, 2) to ensure that the Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises can be effectively assisted
181 with personalized cues for those who need it (e.g., people experiencing freezing of gait or people
182 with small steps and shuffling gait (13-15)). The so-obtained best cues for supporting gait, as
183 evaluated subjectively using both the participant's experience and the therapist's impression, will be
184 used during the remainder of the Strolll AR intervention for those who are deemed to benefit from it.
185 We will document if AR cues are added to Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises, and when
186 applicable, specify the type of AR cues as well as their personalized parameters (intercue distance,
187 height, width, audiofeedback, et cetera).

188 To deliver the Strolll AR intervention, participants in this study will by default be equipped
189 with Magic Leap 2 AR glasses for its unmatched vertical AR field of view. Special insert lenses from
190 a complementary lens kit (supports 8 prescriptions from -2.0 to +3.0) made available at each clinical
191 site will be used to correct vision for people wearing spectacles. In case vision cannot be corrected
192 with these insert lenses (e.g., due to a special prescription not part of the lens kit), either tailored
193 insert lenses will be ordered for Magic Leap 2 or Microsoft HoloLens 2 with a slightly smaller
194 vertical AR field of view will be used which can be worn over spectacles to deliver the intervention.

195 Once the participant is deemed sufficiently capable of using the Strolll AR platform technology
196 independently at home in a safe manner (after training in the clinic with the therapist for one to
197 maximally three sessions of 1 hour in two weeks), the participant will take the AR glasses home
198 together with a complementary SIM-card equipped WiFi router to continue the Strolll AR
199 intervention independently at home. If the Strolll AR intervention at home is not deemed safe or
200 suitable by the therapist, the intervention will stop and the reason for this will be documented by the
201 therapist as part of the clinical feasibility evaluation.

202 **2.2.6. Training with Strolll AR intervention independently at home (6 weeks)**

203 The Strolll AR intervention, integrated with usual care, comprises of a 6-week home-based
204 individualized AR gait-and-balance exercise program assisted with tailored AR cues when deemed
205 beneficial. The AR exercises are designed to train aspects associated with gait, balance and falls risk
206 in a gamified manner to maximize training compliance. Strolll AR comprises seven AR exercises,
207 namely Basketballl, Smash!, Mole Patrolll, Hot Buttons, Puzzle Walk, Wobbly Waiter and Cue
208 Challenge (Figure 4), intended to improve gait, balance and falls risk in people with Parkinson's
209 disease. Exercises that require walking (see Supplementary Material) have optional complementary
210 AR cueing (Smash!, Cue Challenge), integrated cueing (speed cue in Wobbly Waiter) or AR-
211 mediated goal-directedness (the moles in Mole Patrolll, the puzzle pieces in Puzzle Walk), to various
212 degrees enabling and assisting people with more severe mobility impairments to participate. For each
213 AR exercise, feedback of performance in terms of game-play performance metrics and functional
214 performance metrics are given during the exercises. For Basketballl, for example, metrics associated
215 with the number of balls thrown in the basket (game-play performance) and the number of sit-to-
216 stands or squats made (functional performance) are given, derived from AR glasses data. See
217 Supplementary Material for more details on the AR exercises, metrics and types of cues.

218 Participants will be invited by their therapist to use Strolll AR minimally 5 times a week for
219 30 active minutes per day, resulting in the recommended 150 minutes per week (1, 7, 8). They can
220 perform the exercises anytime during the day, in one bout or in multiple chunks during the day, with
221 complementary AR cueing when deemed beneficial. The precise exercises, exercise duration,
222 difficulty level and order will be prescribed by the therapist via the Strolll web portal (Figure 5). This
223 will be evaluated and adjusted on a weekly basis in telephone calls, e-consults or during an onsite
224 therapy session using information of the participant in combination with the feedback from exercises
225 that are reported in the Strolll web portal, such as adherence and game-play and functional
226 performance metrics (cf. Supplementary Material). Adherence will be defined as the percentage of
227 performed over prescribed gait-and-balance exercises (i.e., both frequency and session-duration
228 adherence; (12)). The data on game-play level and performance will be used to evaluate whether the
229 exercise program was both progressive (increase in level) and achievable (consistently high game-
230 play performance scores) as intended. The weekly contact moments with the therapist will also be
231 used to ask if participants experienced any adverse events (safety flags). Specifically, safety will be
232 evaluated as the number of adverse events due to the Strolll AR intervention, such as falls, dizziness,
233 eye strain and headache. Potential technical issues will be documented by the researcher, who will be
234 available to provide technical support during the study based on email or telephone contacts with the
235 participants.

236 **2.2.7. Final assessment (T2): effectiveness and clinical feasibility**

237 To be able to evaluate the effectiveness of the Strolll AR intervention, the therapist will again
238 administer standard clinical tests of gait, balance and falls risk (TUG, FTSTS, 10MWT, Mini-
239 BESTest). Participants will fill out the FES-I questionnaire together with the researcher during a
240 telephone call (Table 1).

241 Clinical feasibility of the Strolll AR platform according to the participants will be assessed in
242 terms of user experience (i.e., the User Experience Questionnaire [UEQ; (34)]), technology
243 acceptance and use (i.e., Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology informed questions;
244 (35)), top-3 barriers and facilitators of Strolll AR, and intervention-specific questions regarding
245 Strolll AR, including cueing if used during the intervention (see the Supplementary Material for the
246 Strolll AR evaluation questionnaire). Participants will also report their falls history during the
247 intervention period. The questionnaires of the final assessment are completed through a telephone
248 call with the participant to ensure comprehensibility, which was first assessed in think-aloud sessions
249 with a number of participants (36). In light of the potential future implementation in the clinical
250 pathway, therapists will also be asked about their experience with Strolll AR through a purpose-made
251 questionnaire, including a top-3 barriers and facilitators (assessed before training their first
252 participants and after training their last participant) and the UEQ (assessed after training their last
253 participant). Furthermore, a focus group with the therapist will be organized after the study for an in-
254 depth evaluation of the top-3 barriers and facilitators.

255 **2.3. Participants**

256 We aim to include 80-100 people with Parkinson's disease in this pragmatic RCT. To be eligible to
257 participate, a person must meet the following criteria:

- 258 • 21 years or older
- 259 • have command of the Dutch language
- 260 • diagnosed with Parkinson's disease according to the UK Parkinson's Disease Brain Bank
261 criteria (stages 1-3 on the Hoehn and Yahr scale)

- 262 • bothersome gait or balance impairments (i.e., negatively affecting their ability to perform
263 their usual daily activities as indicated by the person with Parkinson’s disease and/or their
264 therapist).

265 A potential participant who meets any of the following criteria will be excluded from participation:

- 266 • inability to comply with the protocol, i.e. additional neurological diseases and/or orthopedic
267 problems seriously interfering with gait function
268 • insufficient physical capacity to safely perform the intervention (e.g., frequent faller) or
269 severe cognitive impairments (as observed by the therapist)
270 • visual or hearing impairments (after corrective aids)
271 • inability to walk independently for 30 minutes (in bouts of 5-10 minutes)
272 • severe visual hallucinations or illusions
273 • no stable dosage of medication.

274 Finally, in case potential participants are susceptible to hallucinations, have a history of seizures,
275 have deep brain stimulation, or a pacemaker, it should be discussed with their therapist if they can
276 participate, as per Strolll’s Instructions For Use (DOC-IFU-00021 (NL), Revision 01, Date of Issue
277 06 2024). Participants are not allowed to participate in other intervention studies during the study.
278 Participants will be recruited by their own therapist (see the flowchart in Figure 3 for the procedure).
279 Approximately ten physical or exercise therapy clinics will participate, recruited via regional
280 ParkinsonNet meetings and using a recruitment text. Clinics will be primary care practices that have
281 therapists affiliated with ParkinsonNet (Dutch society for Parkinson’s therapists). Only clinics that
282 indicate that they have the capacity to include minimally 5-10 participants within 6-9 months will be
283 included. Therapists will be trained on how to administer the clinical tests (they are already familiar
284 with most if not all tests as these are typically used tests in clinical practice) to ensure a high
285 interrater reliability, and in applying the in- and exclusion criteria for the selection of eligible
286 participants. In addition, therapists will be trained by the researchers on how to use the AR glasses,
287 the Strolll AR application and the Strolll web portal for remote prescription of and feedback about
288 the Strolll AR intervention. After this initial training, therapists will take the AR glasses home to
289 practice and become familiar with both the Strolll AR application and the Strolll web portal
290 themselves. After practicing for one to two weeks, the researchers will contact the therapist again to
291 discuss the use of the Strolll AR platform and to offer support during the first in-clinic session with
292 Strolll AR with a participant to ensure therapists are well-versed with the study protocol and the
293 Strolll AR platform. Recruitment started in May 2024 and the last T2 assessment is expected in
294 January 2025.

295 **2.4.Sample size calculation**

296 A convenience sample of 80-100 participants will be included and measured from approximately 10
297 clinics in a time frame of 9 months. This sample size will give the therapists of the clinics enough
298 experience with the Strolll AR platform and intervention to evaluate feasibility from a therapists’
299 perspective (e.g., usability, acceptability, safety). For our effectiveness outcomes, an a-priori required
300 sample-size calculation in G*Power 3.1.9.7 showed that 58 participants (i.e., 29 per group) is
301 sufficient for identifying statistically significant between-group differences (usual care vs. Strolll AR
302 intervention). This is based on 80% power and a two-tailed alpha error of 5% and a minimal
303 improvement of 2.57 seconds in TUG (i.e., the average of the smallest detectable TUG difference of
304 Lim et al. (37) and Huang et al. (38)) and an effect size of 0.755 (Cohen’s d statistic; SD of 3.4
305 seconds; (38)). Accounting for approximately 10 dropouts during the usual-care period,

306 approximately 10 dropouts during the pre-intervention in-clinic phase (i.e., participants deemed
307 unable to take the glasses home after one-to-three in-clinic training sessions) and approximately 10
308 dropouts during the intervention period at home (estimates based on Hardeman et al. (12)), recruiting
309 a total of 80-100 participants should be sufficient for obtaining the minimal groups sizes required for
310 identifying between-group differences. As dropout rates are taken into account, participants who are
311 not completing the study will not be replaced. Plans to reduce dropouts are a voucher as a token of
312 appreciation for their participation, updates about study progression via a newsletter send to
313 participants and therapists every two months to keep them involved in the study and having weekly
314 online or onsite check-ins with the participating therapists.

315 **2.5. Discontinuation or modification of allocated intervention**

316 Participants can leave the study at any time for any reason if they wish to do so without any
317 consequences. The researcher can decide to withdraw a participant from the study for urgent medical
318 reasons or when medication dosage is changed during the study. Participants that are withdrawn will
319 not be replaced, because the sample-size calculation takes such dropouts into account. Reasons for
320 drop out or withdrawal will be collected. Dropouts during the intervention period will be asked to
321 complete the UEQ and Stroll AR evaluation questionnaire to reduce potential bias in the study's
322 participant experience results which could become manifest if only data from participants completing
323 the intervention would be taken into account. For the other clinical tests and questionnaires, dropouts
324 will lead to missing data.

325 **2.6. Premature termination of the study**

326 The study will be terminated prematurely if serious adverse events, like falls that lead to
327 hospitalization, related to the Stroll AR intervention at home are reported for more than two
328 participants. A liability insurance is in place in accordance with the legal requirements in the
329 Netherlands, specifically article 7 of the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (in Dutch:
330 Wet Medisch-wetenschappelijk Onderzoek met Mensen, WMO). This insurance provides cover for
331 damage to research participants through injury or death caused by the study. The insurance applies to
332 the damage that becomes apparent during the study or within 4 years after the end of the study.

333 **2.7. Statistical analysis**

334 Data analysis will be performed in JASP (39). Missing data will be excluded analysis-by-analysis.

335 **2.7.1. Group characterization**

336 Descriptive statistics of demographics (i.e., age, gender, disease duration and LEDD) and
337 questionnaires and clinical tests (i.e., MoCA, MDS-UPDRS, NFOGQ, PASE, CIRS and falls history)
338 will be used to characterize the study sample (n=80-100). To identify potential differences between
339 control and intervention groups after the randomizations, independent-samples *t*-tests will be used
340 after confirming normality with Shapiro-Wilk tests (otherwise Mann-Whitney U-tests will be used)
341 for all parameters except gender, for which a Chi-square test will be used to identify between-groups
342 differences.

343 **2.7.2. Feasibility (safety, adherence, performance and user experience)**

344 Clinical feasibility will be evaluated on several aspects. First, to determine if the Stroll AR
345 intervention can be safely performed at home, descriptive outcomes will be reported for safety (i.e.,
346 number of dropouts during training at home including the reasons for withdrawal, adverse events

347 including a paired-samples *t*-test comparison of the average weekly number of falls experienced
348 during usual-care and intervention periods), providing insight into the potential risks of the Stroll
349 AR intervention.

350 Second, to determine if the Stroll AR intervention was adherable over the course of the
351 intervention, we will conduct a repeated-measures one-way ANOVA with the within-subject factor
352 Time (three levels) on adherence scores derived from the first, second and third part of the
353 intervention at home (i.e., default intervention period is 6 weeks, so adherence is derived over
354 roughly two-weeks intervals). The assumption of sphericity will be checked according to Girde
355 (40). If Greenhouse–Geisser’s epsilon exceeds 0.75, the Huynh-Feldt correction will be applied;
356 otherwise, the Greenhouse–Geisser correction will be used. Effect sizes will be quantified with η_p^2 .
357 Paired-samples *t*-tests will be used for post-hoc comparisons of a significant main effect of Time. In
358 addition, one sample *t*-tests against 100% will be performed for adherence scores at each Time point
359 to determine whether or not there were systematic deviations from the prescribed treatment.

360 Third, the pre-cursor of Stroll AR, Reality DTx[®], was found to be a progressive-but-
361 achievable intervention in a research setting (12), where researchers balanced and tailored task
362 demands and capacity (i.e., not too easy to prevent boredom and not too difficult to prevent
363 demotivation) when remotely prescribing the exercises based on weekly telephone calls with the
364 participants and their performance data from the Stroll web portal. To determine if Stroll AR,
365 delivered in the clinical pathway, also results in a progressive-but-achievable intervention (i.e.,
366 increasing exercise levels over weeks whilst maintaining high performance scores), the same one-
367 way repeated measures ANOVA will be performed for game-play levels and performance scores. We
368 expect to find strong main effects of Time for exercise levels (with post-hoc effects showing an
369 increase in exercise levels), but not or less so for performance scores.

370 Fourth, user experience will inform on acceptability among people with Parkinson’s disease
371 (see Supplementary Material for the Stroll AR evaluation questionnaire) and among therapists (i.e.,
372 top-3 barriers and facilitators questionnaire and an in-depth focus group) and usability (UEQ from
373 both participants and therapists) of the Stroll AR intervention. To evaluate participant experience, all
374 participants who started with the Stroll AR intervention in the clinic will be analyzed collectively
375 (i.e., intention-to-treat protocol) to avoid a selection bias of the people who completed the
376 intervention. The UEQ will not be analyzed statistically but will be reported as descriptive outcomes
377 and interpreted against known benchmark scores (34). Also, other participants’ or therapists’ reported
378 outcome measures from the questionnaires will be reported as descriptive outcomes. Finally, the
379 fraction of participants deemed eligible for performing the intervention at home after having had the
380 in-clinic Stroll AR sessions will inform about the usability of the intervention.

381 **2.7.3. Effectiveness**

382 The effectiveness of Stroll AR for improving TUG, FTSTS, 10MWT, Mini-BESTest and FES-I will
383 be analyzed according to the per-protocol principle for participants who have completed the final
384 assessment, randomized into control and intervention groups using the 20 concealed randomizations.
385 For each outcome parameter, independent-samples *t*-tests (or their non-parametric equivalents) will
386 be used to compare Control (i.e., using the change scores during the control period; T0-T1) and
387 Intervention groups (i.e., using the change scores during the intervention period; T1-T2). We expect
388 significantly higher change scores for the Intervention group than for the Control group. The 20
389 predefined concealed randomizations will enable us to perform multiple between-group comparisons,
390 yielding a sensitivity analysis to test the robustness of the effectiveness findings in this pragmatic
391 RCT. That is, this innovative analysis approach will not only provide us with a one-shot indication of
392 the statistical effect, but also with a confidence interval of this effect. Furthermore, multiple
393 randomized comparisons will reduce the likelihood of a systematic confounding effect biasing the

394 pragmatic RCT results, as is often the case when a single one-shot randomization would result in
395 Control and Intervention groups differing significantly in certain demographic or clinical
396 characteristics. With a multiple-shots randomization, potential effects associated with significant
397 between-group differences in demographics or clinical characteristics of a single randomization will
398 average out over the multiple shots.

399 As a secondary analysis, which is possible given the design in which all per-protocol
400 participants performed the same T0-control-T1-intervention-T2 procedure, a complementary within-
401 subjects comparison will be performed using repeated-measures ANOVAs with the within-subject
402 factor Time (three levels: T0, T1, T2) for the TUG, FTSTST, 10MWT, Mini-BESTest and FES-I,
403 comparable to the analysis performed in Hardeman et al. (12). For significant main effects of Time,
404 the first and second reverse Helmert contrasts will be used to evaluate Control and Intervention
405 effects, respectively. This will help us interpret (a potential null-finding of) the pragmatic RCT as
406 such a within-subjects comparison is less susceptible to between-subjects variation than a between-
407 groups comparison.

408 **3. Discussion**

409 The objective of this pragmatic RCT on Strolll AR, an individualized AR gait-and-balance exercise
410 platform complemented with tailored AR cues when deemed beneficial, is to examine its clinical
411 feasibility and effectiveness for improving indicators of gait, balance and falls risk in people with
412 Parkinson's disease. This particular study design will demonstrate feasibility and effectiveness in a
413 real-world setting and for a population representative of people with Parkinson's disease seen in the
414 clinical pathway. The secondary objective of this study is to evaluate procedures for tailoring
415 assistive AR cues to individual people with Parkinson's disease when deemed beneficial for them in
416 performing the AR gait-and-balance exercises.

417 The number of people with chronic neurological disorders like Parkinson's disease waiting
418 for physiotherapy treatment is increasing (41). Due to the growing number of people with a chronic
419 neurological disorder and the limited number of staff available, digital therapeutics solutions emerge
420 such as the Strolll AR platform. Such innovative technologies are well aligned with the mission
421 statement of care in the Netherlands (42, 43), emphasizing the importance of i) care in the home
422 environment if possible, ii) independent care if possible (self-management) and iii) digitally
423 supported care if possible (supported by technology). The Strolll AR platform aligns well with this
424 mission. It is a home-based intervention, which can be executed by the person with Parkinson's
425 disease themselves on AR glasses, remotely prescribed by a therapist. The gamified nature of Strolll
426 AR, combined with the remote prescription and reporting options and data dashboards, also have the
427 potential to increase the adherence to prescribed therapy at home, thereby likely improving treatment
428 effectiveness. Finally, Strolll AR provides people with Parkinson's disease the flexibility,
429 independence and ownership of their rehabilitation to be performed when they feel up for it (e.g.,
430 depending on fatigue and medication levels, which fluctuates during the day) in the convenience of
431 their own home and work/life schedule, allowing for more professionally prescribed treatment
432 sessions and/or treatment hours without the burden and costs associated with commuting to the
433 healthcare professional for a session fitting their time schedule. Hardeman et al. (12) already showed
434 that the precursor of the Strolll AR platform showed promising results in improving indicators of
435 gait, balance and falls risk. Moreover, this then-called Reality DTx[®] AR intervention was safe and
436 deemed acceptable and usable by the participants. The current study builds on these findings, that
437 were obtained in a research setting, by conducting a pragmatic RCT implemented in a representative
438 clinical pathway.

439 For future implementation of Strolll AR, it is important to know, besides its effectiveness in a
440 real-world clinical setting, what the stakeholders think of the intervention. Determining information

441 about the clinical feasibility of Stroll AR, both from therapists' and participants' perspectives, is
442 therefore a key focus of this study. Since the context wherein Stroll AR is evaluated in this study is
443 similar to the clinical pathway for which Stroll AR is intended, the feedback from the questionnaires
444 is representative and relevant for its further development and implementation after study completion.
445 That is, safety, adherence, usability and acceptability feedback might help to optimize the fit between
446 state-of-the-art physiotherapy practice and the Stroll AR platform. Moreover, insights into top
447 barriers and facilitators experienced by therapists will help in choosing the most pertinent
448 implementation strategies (44).

449 Considering the pressing needs for transforming the future of healthcare, AR technology
450 integrated in the clinical pathway of people with Parkinson's disease seems one of the ways to go. It
451 may help in combatting waitlists, in improving accessibility of care, in increasing the number of
452 treatments as well as their adherence, and perhaps even in pivoting from healthcare to care for health,
453 thereby capitalizing on the importance of high-quality exercise in maintaining health and preventing
454 decline. Moreover, Stroll AR may be a platform that facilitates the transition from supervised care in
455 the clinic to independent care at home. That is, if proven effective, Stroll AR could provide a
456 platform for delivering individualized treatment at a high dose and adherence, improving gait,
457 balance and falls risk in people with Parkinson's disease. As such it has the potential for bringing
458 evidence-based rehabilitation into the homes of people with Parkinson's disease (11), thereby
459 fostering longer-term self-management of health and disease. Nevertheless, while technology like AR
460 evolves at a rapid and accelerated pace, changes in clinical practice are typically slow and dependent
461 on a solid evidence base. The innovative design of this particular pragmatic RCT, allowing for
462 studying both the clinical feasibility and effectiveness in a single study design in representative real-
463 world settings, could potentially help speed up the availability of the evidence required for the uptake
464 of technology-driven interventions like Stroll AR in the clinical pathway.

465 **4. Ethics**

466 Ethical approval has been obtained from the accredited Medical Ethics Committee United, the
467 Netherlands (R24.008, NL86191.100.24). The trial has been registered on Clinicaltrials.gov
468 (NCT06590987, published September 10, 2024). Protocol modifications/amendments will be sent to
469 the ethics committee for approval and updated here. Participants will provide their written informed
470 consent obtained by the researchers DG, EH, PD, JB and AD before participating in this study.

471 **5. Data management**

472 Questionnaires and clinical tests collected in the clinic will be collected on paper and will be entered
473 into a digital database (i.e., Castor EDC). Digital copies and an export of the digital database will be
474 stored on a secured drive (i.e., Research Drive). Home questionnaires can also directly be entered
475 into the digital database by the participants using an online questionnaire. Personal data will be
476 handled according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation and the Dutch Act on
477 Implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation. Personal data to contact participants will
478 be stored separately from other data and provided with an ID number. An identification file with
479 codes linking ID numbers to participant numbers (four-digit codes) will be stored in a folder separate
480 from the contact details file with ID numbers. Files with personal data to contact participants and the
481 identification file can only be accessed with a password. Data collected on paper will be stored in a
482 secured cabinet. Administrative data (logbooks for data collection and analysis, manuals, protocols)
483 will be stored on OneDrive to improve interpretation and re-use of the data. All digital drives and
484 databases require multi-factor authentication.

485 **6. Conflict of Interest**

486 MR is a scientific advisor with share options for Strolll Ltd., a digital therapeutics company building
487 AR software for physical rehabilitation, for one day a week ancillary to his main position as associate
488 professor Technology in Motion at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. The other authors declare no
489 conflicts of interest.

490 **7. Author Contributions**

491 DG and MR (principal investigators) were responsible for the conceptualization. DG outlined the
492 study protocol and the pre-registered report. DG and MR were responsible for supervision and
493 funding acquisition. DG, MR, EH and LH were involved in the development of the user experience
494 methodology (e.g., Strolll AR evaluation questionnaire). DG, EH, PD, JB and AD were involved in
495 the execution of the trial. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the
496 manuscript.

497 **8. Funding**

498 This project is funded by the EMIL project financial support to third parties, which is funded by the
499 European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not
500 necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting
501 authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

European Media
and Immersion Lab

502

503 **9. Acknowledgments**

504 The authors would like to thank Marco Hoozemans for his help in shaping the study design. The
505 article is available as a preprint on Zenodo.

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628 **11. Supplementary Material**

- 629 Data sheet 1: Informed consent form
630 Data sheet 2: Strolll AR exercises and cues
631 Data sheet 3: Strolll AR evaluation questionnaire
632 Data sheet 4: SPIRIT checklist

633 **12. Data Availability Statement**

634 The results of this study will be published in international peer-reviewed journals and will be
635 presented at national as well as international scientific conferences, Parkinson association meetings,
636 and social media through professional channels. Anonymized research data will be published as
637 supplemental material in publications or will be made available in a repository and/or from the
638 corresponding author on reasonable request.

639 **Figure legends**

640 **Figure 1.** (A) Example of a Stroll AR gamified gait-and-balance exercise (i.e., Basketball)
641 performed in the clinic under the supervision of a therapist, (B) Example of a Stroll gamified gait-
642 and-balance exercise performed independently at home (i.e., Smash!) complemented with assistive
643 AR cues.

644 **Figure 2.** Schematic of the study design.

645 **Figure 3.** Flowchart from enrollment to statistical analysis.

646 **Figure 4.** Stroll AR gait-and-balance exercises: Smash! (without [A] and with [B] assistive AR
647 cues), Mole Patrol (C), Hot Buttons (D), Basketball (E), Puzzle Walk (F), Wobbly Waiter (G) and
648 Cue Challenge (H).

649 **Figure 5.** Stroll AR web portal for therapists to (remotely) prescribe individualized treatment
650 programs (type and settings of AR exercises, top part) and to see feedback on adherence and game-
651 play performance (session history, lower part).

652 **Table 1.** Overview of T0, T1 and T2 tests and questionnaires to characterize the study sample and to
 653 evaluate the effectiveness and clinical feasibility of the Stroll AR intervention.

	T0	T1	T2
Study sample characterization			
Demographics (age, gender, disease duration)	X		
LEDD	X		
MoCA	X		
MDS-UPDRS	X		
NFOGQ	X		
PASE	X		
CIRS	X		
12-month falls history	X		
Effectiveness			
TUG*	X	X	X
FTSTS	X	X	X
10MWT	X	X	X
Mini-BESTest	X	X	X
FES-I	X	X	X
Clinical feasibility			
Falls history during usual-care and intervention periods		X	X
Stroll AR evaluation questionnaire			X
UEQ			

654 LEDD = Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose; MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment; MDS-UPDRS = Movement
 655 Disorders Society Unified Parkinson Disease Rating; NFOGQ = New Freezing of Gait Questionnaire; PASE = Physical
 656 Activity Scale for the Elderly; CIRS = Cumulative Illness Rating Scale; TUG = Timed Up-and-Go test; FTSTS = Five
 657 Times Sit-to-Stand test; 10MWT = 10-meter walk test; Mini-BESTest = Mini Balance Evaluation Scale Test; FES-I =
 658 Falls Efficacy Scale International; UEQ = User Experience Questionnaire.

659 * Primary outcome measure.

Supplementary Material

Informed consent form

Related to

Strolll AR: Cueing-assisted gamified augmented-reality gait-and-balance rehabilitation at home for people with Parkinson's disease

Team Holocue(X), Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

- I have read the information letter. I was also able to ask questions. My questions have been adequately answered. I had enough time to decide whether I wanted to participate.
- I understand that participation is voluntary. I also know that I can withdraw or stop my participation at any time. I do not have to say why I want to stop.
- I know that I can withdraw my consent for the use of my data. This has no adverse consequences for me as a patient.
- I give the researcher permission to inform my GP that I am participating in this study.
- I give the researchers permission to collect and use my data, such as medication use, disease severity and results of standardized clinical gait and balance tests. The researchers do this only to answer the research question of this study (i.e. determining the clinical feasibility and effectiveness of Strolll AR).
- I know that, for the purpose of checking the quality of the research, some people can view all my data. These people are listed in the information letter. I give these people permission to view my data for this purpose.
- I will return the glasses with the Strolll AR exercise program to the researchers after the training.

- Please indicate 'yes' or 'no' in the table below.

I give permission to store my data for use in other research, as described in the information letter.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission to ask me after this study if I want to participate in a follow-up study.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

- By signing I indicate that I want to participate in this study.

My name is (participant):

Signature:

Date : __ / __ / __

-
I confirm that I have fully informed this participant about the study described above. If information emerges during the research that could influence the participant's willingness to participate, I will inform this participant in a timely manner.

Researcher's name (or representative):.....

Signature:.....

Date: __ / __ / __

Supplementary Material

Table S1: Stroll AR exercises

	Description of the exercise	Exercise settings	Feedback
<p style="text-align: center;">Smash!</p>	<p>A boxing rehabilitation exercise to train gait, dynamic balance, weight shifting and turning.</p> <p>The goal is to smash as many items as possible from two plinths as they appear, demanding alternate left and right punches to promote weight shifting, with available items alternating between the plinths to promote walking and turning.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty level (number of required punches before the items drop from the plinth, 2 – 20 punches) • Distance between the plinths (2 - 10 meters) • Optional addition of cues between plinths (see Table S2 for more details) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and performed punches • Score (number of items smashed) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Meters walked • Number of punches • Score
<p style="text-align: center;">Mole Patroll</p>	<p>A goal-directed walking rehabilitation exercise to train gait initiation, walking adaptability, dynamic balance, turning, stopping and strength (when performed in squat mode).</p> <p>The goal is to stomp as many moles as possible by scanning the room, spotting where they appear, and stomping on them either with both feet or squatting on them (a game-mode setting) before they disappear.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty level (time before mole disappears, 1 – 60 seconds per mole) • Game mode (stomp or squat mode) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (number of moles stomped) • Distance walked <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Meters walked • Score
<p style="text-align: center;">Hot Buttons</p>	<p>A dynamic reaching exercise to train functional reaching, reaction time and dynamic balance.</p> <p>The goal is to press the button that lights up as quickly as possible before it disappears. Feet positioning is controlled to ensure sufficient reach amplitudes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise: (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty level (time before button disappears, 1.5 – 60 seconds time out) • Game mode (free standing, wall, table) • Game mode (3, 6 or 9 buttons) • Game mode (random, left hand only, right hand only) • Distance (reach distance between user and board, 40 – 90 centimeters) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (number of buttons pressed including bonus points for streaks which add up dependent on the number of buttons hit in a row, you lose the streak when hitting a button with the wrong hand) • Number of buttons pressed in a streaks (i.e., pressing two or more buttons in a row with the prescribed hand) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Number of buttons pressed • Score

<p>Basketball</p>	<p>A sit-to-stand rehabilitation exercise to train dynamic balance and lower-limb muscle strength.</p> <p>The goal is to score as many points as possible by completing sit-to-stand or squat-to-stand movements (a game-mode setting) to spawn a set of three basketballs, and throw them into the hoop.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise: (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty level (number of required sit-to-stands or squats per three balls, 1 - 9 sit-to-stand/squat) • Game mode (sit-to-stand, squat mode) • Rhythmic music (on, off) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and performed sit-to-stands or squats • Number of basketballs scored • Score (number of sit-to-stands or squats plus two times the number of basketballs scored) <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Number of sit-to-stands or squats • Basketballs scored • Score
<p>Puzzle Walk</p>	<p>A goal-directed walking rehabilitation exercise to train gait, dynamic balance, turning, stopping and functional reaching.</p> <p>The goal is to find puzzle pieces in the room, pick them up by reaching and grabbing them with your hand and then placing them on the easel to complete the puzzle before the time runs out.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty level (number of puzzle pieces, 4 – 48 pieces) • Game mode (puzzle piece height: high, hip, knee, floor) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of prescribed and collected puzzle pieces <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (number of collected puzzle pieces within the set game duration, bonus points for every second left on the clock) <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Meters walked • Score
<p>Wobbly Waiter</p>	<p>A cued rehabilitation exercise focusing on walking at a set speed, turning and standing-up/sitting-down up from/in a chair, with an element of cognitive challenge while seated (memory retention).</p> <p>The goal is to memorize a cafe order from a customer, assemble the order by selecting the buttons with the correct food items in the right sequence, and deliver the order to the customer's table within a prescribed amount of time, as cued by the waiter's speed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1 - 10 minutes) • Difficulty Level (number of items to remember, 3 – 6 items) • 10-meter walk test (results) • Timed Up-and-Go test (results) • Gait speed adjustment (+/- 25%) 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive results (number of items correctly remembered) • Money collected • Prescribed and performed completion durations <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (money collected) <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Meters walked • Score • Cognitive results • completion (sub) durations

<p>Cue Challenge</p>	<p>A cue evaluation and gait training exercise designed to try a variety of cues and find the one that works best for the participant. Cue Challenge comes with a multitude of settings to personalize the cues. Cue Challenge can be prescribed for gait training, modifying gait characteristics like step length and cadence with cue settings like intercue distances, along tracks that can be adjusted in terms of track shape, turning options, cue types, sizes and colors.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of the exercise (1 - 10 minutes) • Track (straight, oval, figure of eight, loop, navigation) • Turning direction (left, right) • Optional addition of cues to modify gait characteristics (see Table S2 for more details) • Optional Likert survey questions to record cue preference 	<p><i>In-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meters walked • Laps completed <p><i>Post-game feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (meters walked) <p><i>Web portal feedback</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prescribed and active minutes • Meters walked • Laps completed • Score • Answer to the Likert survey questions
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Table S2: Stroll AR cues

	Description of the cue	Setting options
<p style="text-align: center;">Lines</p>	<p>A series of flat, 2D colored lines on the ground in front of the user to step over.</p>	<p>Color, step length, line width and line thickness.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Obstacles</p>	<p>A series of 3D colored obstacles on the ground in front of the user to step over.</p>	<p>Color, step length, obstacle width, obstacle height, and obstacle thickness.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Rhythm</p>	<p>An audible cue, with different action oriented rhythmic audio sounds for the user to step in time to.</p>	<p>Sound, volume, and speed (beats per minute).</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Dinosaur footprints</p>	<p>A series of dinosaur footprints on the ground in front of a user to step on with audible feedback (mud sound).</p>	<p>Step length and step width.</p>

Supplementary Material

Strolll AR evaluation questionnaire

Technology acceptance

The questions below are about the Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises. For each of the following statements, indicate to what extent you agree with the statement.

	Totally disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Totally agree
1. I now know how to use Strolll AR.					
2. It was easy to independently use Strolll AR.					
3. In case of technical problems with Strolll AR, I could get help from someone.					
4. It was easy to learn how Strolll AR works.					
5. I would like to use Strolll AR regularly if I could keep the glasses.					
6. My living environment is suitable for the use of Strolll AR.					
7. My therapist encouraged the use of Strolll AR throughout the study.					
8. Strolll AR helps me to improve my gait and balance.					
9. Strolll AR helps me to be more physically active.					
10. I find Strolll AR useful to use at home to train gait and balance.					

11. I would continue to train with Strolll AR if I could keep the glasses.					
12. It was clear and understandable how Strolll AR works.					
13. People who are important to me encouraged me to use Strolll AR.					
14. It was easy to get comfortable using Strolll AR.					
15. Using Strolll AR can improve my physical health.					
16. I would like to continue using Strolll AR in the future.					
17. People who influence my behavior encouraged me to use Strolll AR.					

Technology use

1. Do you use a laptop or computer?

- Yes
- Yes, but with help
- No

2. Do you use a smartphone?

- Yes
- Yes, but with help
- No

3. Do you use a tablet?

- Yes
- Yes, but with help
- No

4. How often do you use the internet?

- Rarely/never
- Once a week
- A few times a week
- Once a day
- Several times a day

5. How often do you read or send emails?

- Rarely/never
- Once a week
- A few times a week
- Once a day
- Several times a day

6. How often do you use apps (e.g., weather, navigation, calendar, video calling, internet banking, games)

- Rarely/never
- Once a week
- A few times a week
- Once a day
- Several times a day

Top-3 barriers and facilitators of Strolll AR

This top-3 barriers and facilitators is about the Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises performed at home prescribed and individualized by the therapist. Fill out the top 3 based on what you know about Strolll AR and based on what you have experienced during the study. There are no right or wrong answers. Try to answer as honestly as possible.

What do you think are the **main advantages** of Strolll AR for you as a person with Parkinson's disease if you could use Strolll AR in the future? Give a **top 3** and rank the advantages in order of importance, with the most important advantage at 1. Give a brief explanation of each advantage.

1. _____

Explanation: _____

2. _____

Explanation: _____

3. _____

Explanation: _____

What do you think are the **main disadvantages** of Strolll AR for you as a person with Parkinson's disease if you could use Strolll AR in the future? Give a **top 3** and rank the disadvantages in order of importance, with the most important disadvantage at 1. Give a brief explanation of each disadvantage.

1. _____

Explanation: _____

2. _____

Explanation: _____

3. _____

Explanation: _____

Intervention-specific questions

For each of the following statements, indicate to what extent you agree with the statement.

The questions below are about the Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises

1. To be able to train with Strolll AR, I had to give up other daily activities.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

If you had to give up any daily activities, please indicate what they were:

2. Training at home with Strolll AR is a good addition to my current (physio)therapy.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

3. I enjoyed training with Strolll AR whenever it fitted my schedule.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

4. I enjoyed training in my own home.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

5. I found the remote supervision of the therapist sufficient to be able to train with Strolll AR.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

6. The fact that the therapist can see remotely if I did my exercises at home motivates me to train.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral

- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you please explain your answer?

7. I felt safe while training at home with Strolll AR.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

8. During the training with Strolll AR, I was afraid of falling.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

You should answer the question below on a scale of 0-10. A 0 means 'very unlikely' and a 10 means 'very likely'.

9. How likely are you to recommend the Strolll AR gait-and-balance exercises to a friend (with Parkinson's disease)?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Very unlikely

Very likely

The questions below are about the use of the assistance module or cues. These are for example the visual stripes or rhythms to support walking.

10. Did you use the cues (for example the lines on the floor) in *Smash!* (boxing exercise)?

Yes

No

If you answered 'No' to question 10, you do not need to answer question 11.

11. How did the cues help you?

Supporting freezing (i.e., the feeling of being stuck to the ground)

Taking bigger steps

Increasing stability while walking

Navigating where I needed to go

Helping me to lift my feet

Other, namely _____

12. I found the cues during *Smash!* helpful.

Totally disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

Cue Challenge is the exercise where you walked with different types of cues.

13. Did you play *Cue Challenge* at home?

- Yes
- No

If you answered 'No' to question 13, you do not need to answer question 14.

14. How did *Cue Challenge* help you?

- Supporting freezing (i.e., the feeling of being stuck to the ground)
- Taking bigger steps
- Increasing stability while walking
- Navigating where I needed to go
- Helping me to lift my feet
- Other, namely _____

15. I found playing *Cue Challenge* useful.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Can you explain your answer?

SPIRIT 2013 Checklist: Recommended items to address in a clinical trial protocol and related documents*

Section/item	Item No	Description	Addressed on page number
Administrative information			
Title	1	Descriptive title identifying the study design, population, interventions, and, if applicable, trial acronym	1
Trial registration	2a	Trial identifier and registry name. If not yet registered, name of intended registry	1
	2b	All items from the World Health Organization Trial Registration Data Set	1,2,12
Protocol version	3	Date and version identifier	1
Funding	4	Sources and types of financial, material, and other support	12
Roles and responsibilities	5a	Names, affiliations, and roles of protocol contributors	1,12
	5b	Name and contact information for the trial sponsor	12
	5c	Role of study sponsor and funders, if any, in study design; collection, management, analysis, and interpretation of data; writing of the report; and the decision to submit the report for publication, including whether they will have ultimate authority over any of these activities	NA
	5d	Composition, roles, and responsibilities of the coordinating centre, steering committee, endpoint adjudication committee, data management team, and other individuals or groups overseeing the trial, if applicable (see Item 21a for data monitoring committee)	NA

Introduction

Background and rationale	6a	Description of research question and justification for undertaking the trial, including summary of relevant studies (published and unpublished) examining benefits and harms for each intervention	2,3
	6b	Explanation for choice of comparators	3
Objectives	7	Specific objectives or hypotheses	3
Trial design	8	Description of trial design including type of trial (eg, parallel group, crossover, factorial, single group), allocation ratio, and framework (eg, superiority, equivalence, noninferiority, exploratory)	3

Methods: Participants, interventions, and outcomes

Study setting	9	Description of study settings (eg, community clinic, academic hospital) and list of countries where data will be collected. Reference to where list of study sites can be obtained	3
Eligibility criteria	10	Inclusion and exclusion criteria for participants. If applicable, eligibility criteria for study centres and individuals who will perform the interventions (eg, surgeons, psychotherapists)	6,7
Interventions	11a	Interventions for each group with sufficient detail to allow replication, including how and when they will be administered	4,5
	11b	Criteria for discontinuing or modifying allocated interventions for a given trial participant (eg, drug dose change in response to harms, participant request, or improving/worsening disease)	8
	11c	Strategies to improve adherence to intervention protocols, and any procedures for monitoring adherence (eg, drug tablet return, laboratory tests)	8
	11d	Relevant concomitant care and interventions that are permitted or prohibited during the trial	7
Outcomes	12	Primary, secondary, and other outcomes, including the specific measurement variable (eg, systolic blood pressure), analysis metric (eg, change from baseline, final value, time to event), method of aggregation (eg, median, proportion), and time point for each outcome. Explanation of the clinical relevance of chosen efficacy and harm outcomes is strongly recommended	3-5
Participant timeline	13	Time schedule of enrolment, interventions (including any run-ins and washouts), assessments, and visits for participants. A schematic diagram is highly recommended (see Figure)	3

Sample size	14	Estimated number of participants needed to achieve study objectives and how it was determined, including clinical and statistical assumptions supporting any sample size calculations	7,8
Recruitment	15	Strategies for achieving adequate participant enrolment to reach target sample size	7

Methods: Assignment of interventions (for controlled trials)

Allocation:

Sequence generation	16a	Method of generating the allocation sequence (eg, computer-generated random numbers), and list of any factors for stratification. To reduce predictability of a random sequence, details of any planned restriction (eg, blocking) should be provided in a separate document that is unavailable to those who enrol participants or assign interventions	3,9,10
Allocation concealment mechanism	16b	Mechanism of implementing the allocation sequence (eg, central telephone; sequentially numbered, opaque, sealed envelopes), describing any steps to conceal the sequence until interventions are assigned	3,9,10
Implementation	16c	Who will generate the allocation sequence, who will enrol participants, and who will assign participants to interventions	3,9,10
Blinding (masking)	17a	Who will be blinded after assignment to interventions (eg, trial participants, care providers, outcome assessors, data analysts), and how	3
	17b	If blinded, circumstances under which unblinding is permissible, and procedure for revealing a participant's allocated intervention during the trial	NA

Methods: Data collection, management, and analysis

Data collection methods	18a	Plans for assessment and collection of outcome, baseline, and other trial data, including any related processes to promote data quality (eg, duplicate measurements, training of assessors) and a description of study instruments (eg, questionnaires, laboratory tests) along with their reliability and validity, if known. Reference to where data collection forms can be found, if not in the protocol	3-5
	18b	Plans to promote participant retention and complete follow-up, including list of any outcome data to be collected for participants who discontinue or deviate from intervention protocols	8

Data management	19	Plans for data entry, coding, security, and storage, including any related processes to promote data quality (eg, double data entry; range checks for data values). Reference to where details of data management procedures can be found, if not in the protocol	11
Statistical methods	20a	Statistical methods for analysing primary and secondary outcomes. Reference to where other details of the statistical analysis plan can be found, if not in the protocol	8-10
	20b	Methods for any additional analyses (eg, subgroup and adjusted analyses)	8-10
	20c	Definition of analysis population relating to protocol non-adherence (eg, as randomised analysis), and any statistical methods to handle missing data (eg, multiple imputation)	8-10
Methods: Monitoring			
Data monitoring	21a	Composition of data monitoring committee (DMC); summary of its role and reporting structure; statement of whether it is independent from the sponsor and competing interests; and reference to where further details about its charter can be found, if not in the protocol. Alternatively, an explanation of why a DMC is not needed	NA
	21b	Description of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines, including who will have access to these interim results and make the final decision to terminate the trial	NA
Harms	22	Plans for collecting, assessing, reporting, and managing solicited and spontaneously reported adverse events and other unintended effects of trial interventions or trial conduct	6,8
Auditing	23	Frequency and procedures for auditing trial conduct, if any, and whether the process will be independent from investigators and the sponsor	NA
Ethics and dissemination			
Research ethics approval	24	Plans for seeking research ethics committee/institutional review board (REC/IRB) approval	11
Protocol amendments	25	Plans for communicating important protocol modifications (eg, changes to eligibility criteria, outcomes, analyses) to relevant parties (eg, investigators, REC/IRBs, trial participants, trial registries, journals, regulators)	11

Consent or assent	26a	Who will obtain informed consent or assent from potential trial participants or authorised surrogates, and how (see Item 32)	4,11
	26b	Additional consent provisions for collection and use of participant data and biological specimens in ancillary studies, if applicable	NA
Confidentiality	27	How personal information about potential and enrolled participants will be collected, shared, and maintained in order to protect confidentiality before, during, and after the trial	11
Declaration of interests	28	Financial and other competing interests for principal investigators for the overall trial and each study site	11,12
Access to data	29	Statement of who will have access to the final trial dataset, and disclosure of contractual agreements that limit such access for investigators	15
Ancillary and post-trial care	30	Provisions, if any, for ancillary and post-trial care, and for compensation to those who suffer harm from trial participation	8
Dissemination policy	31a	Plans for investigators and sponsor to communicate trial results to participants, healthcare professionals, the public, and other relevant groups (eg, via publication, reporting in results databases, or other data sharing arrangements), including any publication restrictions	8
	31b	Authorship eligibility guidelines and any intended use of professional writers	NA
	31c	Plans, if any, for granting public access to the full protocol, participant-level dataset, and statistical code	15
Appendices			
Informed consent materials	32	Model consent form and other related documentation given to participants and authorised surrogates	15
Biological specimens	33	Plans for collection, laboratory evaluation, and storage of biological specimens for genetic or molecular analysis in the current trial and for future use in ancillary studies, if applicable	NA

*It is strongly recommended that this checklist be read in conjunction with the SPIRIT 2013 Explanation & Elaboration for important clarification on the items. Amendments to the protocol should be tracked and dated. The SPIRIT checklist is copyrighted by the SPIRIT Group under the Creative Commons [“Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs 3.0 Unported”](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/3.0/) license.